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RESEARCH ARTICLE

LEVERAGING ICT FOR ONLINE JOURNALISM IN THE NIGERIAN BLOGOSPHERE

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ABSTRACT

It is evident that Information Communication Technology (ICT) has revolutionized blogging from a personal online diary to a news dissemination platform. The various innovations of ICT in internet connectivity, mobile technologies, social media, content management tools, and multimedia technologies have enabled bloggers to become online journalists. The purpose of this study was to critically assess the use of ICT innovations in online journalism within the context of the blogosphere of Nigeria, including aspects of credibility, sustainability, and professionalism of blogging. Although it is evident that ICT innovations have reduced the threshold of entry into the profession of journalism by allowing every person to become a journalist through the use of the internet and other media platforms, this study posits that the major problem facing the profession of blogging in Nigeria is not the use of ICT innovations but the lack of professionalism of journalists. The study was developed by applying the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and was conducted as a conceptual study through a qualitative literature review of scholarly works published about two decades ago. The findings of this study revealed that although the use of ICT innovations such as social media and mobile technologies is highly adopted by Nigerians. However, the findings of the study showed that even though ICT innovations such as social media and mobile technologies are highly adopted by Nigerian bloggers due to a low level of complexity and a high level of compatibility, the utilization of ICT innovations for credible online journalism is low. The conclusion of this study is that Nigerian bloggers need to be more professional, need to know more things, and need to have rules to follow in order for blogging to be considered a real way of doing journalism in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS

Blogsphere, online journalism, blogging, ICT, digital media, mobile technology

Introduction

There has been a tremendous revolution in online journalism over the past decades, and this has been driven by the development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). One of the most interesting aspects of online revolution in journalism is the development of blogging as a way of doing online journalism. Although blogging was initially developed as a personal online diary in the late 1990s, it has developed into a powerful way for individuals and groups to become involved in public discourse,

thereby promoting the democratization of information production and dissemination (Rettberg, 2014).

This is because the emergence of the blogosphere, which is a community of blogs and online content creators, has revolutionized conventional journalistic processes through the promotion of decentralized modes of content production, thereby diminishing the role of gatekeeping in the journalistic field (Bruns, 2008). This is

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because, in the blogosphere, an individual without any formal training in journalism has the potential of reaching a wider audience through the use of different digital tools, thereby promoting the concept of citizen journalism, which is a phenomenon where individuals participate in the production of news, thereby broadening the scope of perspectives in the media landscape (Allan & Thorsen, 2009).

In Nigeria, blogging has been on the increase thus expanding the blogosphere as a result of an increase in the use of mobile devices and internet users. Bloggers have a role to play in news dissemination and shaping of public opinion. Nevertheless, there is a major need for evaluation of news credibility and sustainability of online journalism in Nigeria. Some studies (Uche, 2021; Uche et al., 2025) have shown that the way digital media works in Nigeria is based on aspects such as how visible something is online and how many people engage with it. Sometimes this means that speed and popularity are more important than accuracy and professionalism.

Furthermore, there is a lot of misinformation online which raises questions about how reliable blogging is to share news. While technology has made it easier for people to share their ideas it has also made it easier to spread information. This is especially true in places where there is not regulation or professional oversight. Despite a lot of research on journalism there is not much focus on the specific challenges that Nigeria faces. So, there is a gap in understanding how technology can be used to support online journalism in Nigeria.

This study argues that while technology has made it easier for people to start blogging in Nigeria the biggest challenges are not about technology but about adopting standards and using digital tools effectively. The study looks at how Nigerian bloggers use technology what challenges they face and what strategies can be used to make blogging better.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to examine how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is leveraged for online journalism within the Nigerian blogosphere. Furthermore, the study interrogates issues that border around key ICT tools adopted by Nigerian bloggers, factors that influence adoption and use, identifying major challenges confronting effective use of ICT for online journalism, and proposing context specific strategies to enhance sustainability, credibility and professionalism.

Methodology

The study adopted a conceptual study design with a qualitative literature review approach in evaluating the possible ways of leveraging the application of ICT in the practice of online journalism in the Nigerian blogosphere. To ensure the study's reliability, a rigorous literature search was conducted through the utilization of online academic databases like Google Scholar, Scopus, and JSTOR, among other relevant literature from the industry. Some of the keywords used in the search include "ICT and journalism in Nigeria," "blogging in Africa," "digital media Nigeria," "citizen journalism," "online journalism tools," "social media and news dissemination."

The study's literature search covered materials published in about two decades ago; however, emphasis was placed on the utilization of literature published from 2018 to 2025, as it provides a clearer reflection of the realities of the Nigerian online media. Even though the study design provides room for a broader analysis of the themes of the study, it is important to note that the study's limitation lies in the fact that it is a conceptual study. It lacks empirical data; however, it provides a foundation for future empirical study.

The Concept of Blogging, Bloggers and Blogosphere

Blogging is the art of creating content for a particular niche online. It is a form of news and content generation usually by an individual or group of individuals under a given name. In other words, each blog has a particular name attached to it or that describes it. One who engages in blogging is known as a blogger. A blogger often concentrates on the creation of online content in a particular niche. Blogosphere on the other hand is the online environment within which blogging takes place. These days many young people and adults alike especially those who are internet savvy engage in blogging some as a pastime and others as a means of livelihood. In Nigeria for instance, there are notable bloggers whose names ring a bell in the public space. These individuals have developed their blogs or web blogs to the extent that they engage and employ several hands to help them generate content just as in conventional media outfits.

A major distinction between conventional media outlets and blogs is that the latter is strictly practised in an online environment. Without internet infrastructure such as network connectivity from an internet service provider and internet-enabled devices such as mobile phones, laptops and computers, such a practice cannot be guaranteed. More often, bloggers function as online journalists by providing breaking news, commentary and in-depth analysis on various topics. Bloggers operate as independent individuals or in a small group unlike what is obtained in traditional media outlets. It is this freedom and independence that ensures diverse perspectives and voices thus contributing to a more pluralistic media landscape (Kuhn, 2007). The entire blogging space that includes blogs, bloggers and their various readerships forms what is described as the blogosphere.

The Evolution of Blogging

Blogging has a long history that spans over two decades. The art of blogging has also undergone incredible transformations during those years (Gunn, 2024). The art of blogging started as personal online diaries. Later it transformed into an outlet for information and news dissemination. The inception of user-friendly platforms for blogging such as WordPress, Tumblr, and Blogger, along with the rise of social media, help in facilitating this transformation. According to Rettberg (2014), these platforms allow individuals to become publishers by using the tools provided on these platforms, thereby making the process of creating content simpler.

Blogs have been in existence for quite some time, even before the advent of the Internet. The first blog was established in 1994 by Justin Hall, and it was known as Links.net, where individuals would share their lives and thoughts. Later, other bloggers came on board and created their own blogs, known as Online Diaries or Personal Pages,

which were also known as "weblogs" or "Personal Pages." The first journalist to blog an event was Jonathan Dube, who did this in 1998, and Open Diary was born, allowing common people to blog as well. The name "weblog" was later removed in 1999, and three different platforms were introduced: Xanga, LiveJournal, and Blogger. Xanga was meant to be social, while LiveJournal was meant to be a tool for recording thoughts and creating communities. The third one, Blogger, was introduced by Pyra Labs as a commercial blogging tool, which was later acquired by Google in 2003, thereby moving blogging into the mainstream. The early 2000s saw the emergence of BlogAds, Technorati, blogs like Gizmodo and Gawker while Google's purchase of Blogger and AdSense in 2003 further altered the blogosphere.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded on the Diffusion of Innovation Theory as postulated by Everett M. Rogers in 2003. This theory provides a useful analytical framework for the study of the diffusion, adoption, and usage of new technology within a given social system. Daramola (2003) in Anaeto et al. (2008), describes diffusion of innovation theory as a theory that is concerned with seeking the dissemination of information about recent discoveries to the populace within a social set-up. In the context of this study, the theory provides valuable insights into the diffusion and usage of ICT tools by Nigerian bloggers in the field of online journalism.

According to the Diffusion of Innovation Theory, the diffusion of innovation is influenced by the following factors: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability (Rogers, 2003). In the context of ICT tool diffusion in the Nigerian blogosphere, the theory provides valuable insights into the diffusion and usage of ICT tools by Nigerian bloggers.

First, the principle of relative advantage provides a framework for understanding the adoption of ICT tools like social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, X, and WhatsApp) among Nigerian bloggers. Relative advantage refers to the superiority of a technology over traditional media platforms in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, and reach (Hall & Khan, 2002; Borgman, 2000). Indeed, the advantages of social media platforms have contributed significantly to their adoption among both professional and amateur bloggers in Nigeria.

Second, the principle of compatibility is also important in understanding the adoption of ICT tools among Nigerian bloggers. In this context, the principle of compatibility refers to the compatibility of ICT tools with the socio-cultural context of the Nigerian society. For instance, ICT tools like mobile-based platforms have a high level of compatibility with the socio-cultural context of the Nigerian society. Indeed, the mobile-based communication platforms have a high level of compatibility with the communication patterns of the Nigerian people.

Third, the level of complexity of a technology also influences its adoption. While social media platforms have a low level of complexity, Content Management Systems (CMS) have a high level of complexity. Indeed, the low level of complexity of social media platforms has contributed significantly to their adoption among Nigerian bloggers.

Fourth, the concept of trialability, or the degree to which an innovation can be tried on a limited basis, has contributed to the rapid adoption of blogging as a practice. ICTs have provided many tools that allow individuals to create accounts, disseminate content, and experiment with engagement approaches without much financial risk. This has reduced the barriers to participation in the blogosphere.

Fifth, the concept of observability, or the degree to which the results of innovations are visible, has also contributed to the adoption of blogging as a practice. The fact that many of the prominent bloggers in Nigeria are celebrated ICT influencers has made the benefits of blogging more visible, thereby motivating others to adopt similar approaches.

In addition to the five innovation attributes, Roger's innovation theory also recognizes the importance of innovation communication channels or social systems in the innovation diffusion process. The blogosphere in Nigeria is a dynamic social system in which information about new ICT tools, trends, and approaches disseminates rapidly through social interactions among individuals. While the social system facilitates the rapid adoption of blogging as a practice, it is not clear whether the diffusion of ethical standards is keeping pace.

More so, this study contends that whereas the diffusion of ICT tools among the Nigerian blogosphere has been fast and widespread, the diffusion of professional journalistic norms among the same population has been slow. This, therefore, presents a structural imbalance in the sense that the adoption of technology far outstrips the adoption of professional ethics. Consequently, problems like misinformation, lack of credibility, and lack of stability in monetization remain a challenge despite the widespread adoption of ICT tools.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory, therefore, not only explains the adoption of ICT tools among the Nigerian blogging population but also provides a framework for understanding the disconnect between technology adoption and professional practice. This disconnect is important in repositioning the blogging profession as a credible form of online journalism in Nigeria.

ICT Tools and the Practice of Online Journalism in the Nigerian Blogosphere

There are several ICT tools that have proven very essential in the practice of blogging. Some of the ICT tools and technologies that facilitate blogging, which the blogging population utilize, include social media platforms, content management system (CMS), search engine optimisation (SEO), mobile technologies (smartphones and tablets), and multimedia tools. Such tools have enabled the instantaneous reportage of information from anywhere and at any time; thereby adding authenticity and immediacy to bloggers' content (Goggin, 2011).

However, according to Johnson (2016), with high-speed internet connectivity, bloggers can share their information with a wide audience within a short period. Among the most widely used ICT tools in Nigeria is social media platforms like Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, and WhatsApp. This can be explained by their relative advantage and compatibility with Nigeria's digital

environment. This allows bloggers to share information with a wide audience within a short period at a low cost. For example, WhatsApp can be regarded as a widely used tool for sharing news due to its simplicity and low data consumption rate (Uche & Obiora, 2016). However, despite their relative advantages and wide use in sharing information with a wide audience within a short period, their algorithm-based operation may result in a focus on speed rather than accuracy, thereby raising concerns over their credibility (Ogola, 2021).

The second important class of ICT tools is the Content Management Systems (CMS), which includes WordPress and Joomla. This class of tools enables the creation, editing, and publication of online contents (Marlow, 2006). From the perspective of the Diffusion of Innovation Theory, the adoption of CMS tools is characterized by a high level of relative advantage in terms of content organization, branding, and sustainability. However, the adoption of the tool is also influenced by the level of complexity. In essence, the tool requires a certain level of technical knowledge for its optimal utilization. As a result, the majority of Nigerian bloggers do not fully exploit the potentials of the tool, especially in terms of advanced features like search engine optimization (SEO), utilization of multimedia, among others.

The third important class of ICT tools is Mobile technologies, such as mobile phones and tablets, are the major facilitators of online journalism in Nigeria. This is because the majority of the users adopt mobile technologies due to their high compatibility with their lifestyles and the falling costs of mobile devices. The mobile phone has helped bloggers to access, create, and disseminate their content from anywhere, thus improving their immediacy and responsiveness. This is in line with the trialability concept, where mobile phone users can easily test the use of mobile content creation features, such as the camera, audio recording, and video recording, among others, without incurring significant costs.

On the other hand, the availability of multimedia tools has helped to expand the scope of blogging by providing bloggers with the ability to create content in different and more engaging forms. This has improved the observability of the advantages of blogging, as the content created by bloggers has the ability to attract the attention of the audience, thus becoming more observable to other bloggers. The use of multimedia tools, however, has been limited by the technical and resource skills of the bloggers.

In addition, the availability of data analytics and search engine optimisation (SEO) tools also presents another important, albeit underutilised, aspect of the ICT continuum in the Nigerian blogosphere. By extension, the tools promise a great relative advantage for the blogging community in Nigeria, especially in the pursuit of sustainability. However, the adoption of the tools is hindered by their complexity and lack of awareness, which translates into the bloggers' inability to strategically position their works in the face of a growing competitive online environment (Nieborg & Poell, 2018).

Nevertheless, whereas the availability of ICT tools is widespread and growing in the Nigerian blogosphere, the utilisation of the tools is largely

confined to basic functionalities that centre on the themes of immediacy and convenience. Consequently, the diffusion of the advanced utilisation of the tools is hindered by a number of factors, which underscores the earlier submission that the challenge facing the online journalism sphere in Nigeria is not the lack of ICT tools per se, but the level of utilisation of the tools from a professional perspective.

Challenges Confronting Blogging

Aside from the several advantages inherent in the deployment of ICT for Online Journalism by bloggers, there are however several challenges that need to be overcome. Some of which include lack of trust and credibility questions. Uche et al. (2021) noted that because of the non-existence of editorial oversight and gatekeepers, online journalism as practised by bloggers often leads to the spread of fake news and misinformation. There is also the challenge of monetisation as many bloggers are plying their trade for commercial purposes. Thus, for sustainability, they often monetise their content (Goldstein & Rotich, 2008).

There are also ethical and legal issues such as defamation, copyright infringement, and privacy invasion which if not handled usually drag the bloggers to endless legal battles with some authorities and regulatory agencies. The diffusion of ethical standards and journalistic gatekeeping mechanisms has been comparatively slow. This imbalance creates an environment where speed and virality are often prioritised over accuracy and verification, thereby eroding public trust in online content (Ogola, 2021; Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018).

Furthermore, there is the incidence of information overload. The multiplicity of blogs occasioned by ICT can overwhelm their audiences thereby making it near impossible to discern and decipher genuine and quality content (Rettberg, 2014). Other challenges include the exorbitant price of data and internet connectivity, lack of digital literacy, cybersecurity issues, and epileptic power supply, among others (Sanusi & Opaleke, 2024).

The issue of credibility is also a major factor in the Nigerian blogosphere. This is attributed to a lack of institutional gatekeeping, which, although has provided room for access, has also allowed for the proliferation of misinformation. This is also a reflection of the structural imbalance between the rate of innovation in blogging and the rate of diffusion of ethical standards, as discussed in the theory of Diffusion of Innovation.

Additionally, there is the issue of instability of monetization models, which affects the sustainability of blogging as a form of journalism. This is because, although there are numerous opportunities for income generation through ICT platforms, there are also structural challenges in the Nigerian digital economy, which include the low returns from advertising (Uche & Obiora, 2024; Dunu et al., 2017). Admittedly, there are a number of successful bloggers which might encourage widespread adoption; however, such success is often not easily replicable, leading to unrealistic expectations and financial instability among emerging bloggers (Nieborg & Poell, 2018).

Strategic Approaches to Leveraging ICT for Sustainable and Credible Online Journalism in Nigeria

To address the challenges facing online journalism in the Nigerian blogosphere, it is not just a matter of improving access to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) but rather leveraging it strategically and professionally in an enabling environment.

The following strategic approaches can be leveraged by bloggers for credible and sustainable online journalism practice in Nigeria:

1. Establishment of Professional Standards and Ethical Practice

One of the fundamental strategies to be adopted for leveraging ICT for sustainable and credible online journalism in Nigeria is the institutionalisation of professional standards and ethical practice. As discussed earlier in this essay, although there is exponential growth in the use of ICT in Nigeria, there is no exponential growth in journalism practice. To address this problem and improve the quality and relevance of blog content, there is a need to institutionalise principles of fact-checking, verification of sources, and editorial responsibility. This will be done by exposing bloggers to training and certification in ethical practice and fact-checking. This will improve their quality and relevance of content (Bruns & Highfield, 2012).

2. Development of Digital Literacy and Capacity Building

There is a need for capacity building in the development of digital literacy in Nigeria, particularly among bloggers. Although most bloggers in Nigeria have adopted the use of basic ICT tools, the use of advanced tools, such as data analysis, search engine optimisation, and multimedia production, still presents a challenge due to a lack of skills in these tools. Capacity building can help in reducing the perceived difficulty of these tools, thereby promoting the use of these tools by bloggers in Nigeria. This can help bloggers in Nigeria move from the conventional use of basic tools for information dissemination to a more strategic approach in journalism.

3. Diversification of Monetisation Models

Another important strategy for promoting the growth of blogging in Nigeria lies in the diversification of monetisation models. The growth of blogging in Nigeria can be considered sustainable in the long term based on the ability of bloggers in the country to sustain themselves financially from the activity. This calls for a move away from the conventional advertising approach used in monetising blogs towards a diversified approach in monetising blogs in Nigeria.

4. Strengthening regulatory awareness and legal compliance

Moreover, the strengthening of regulatory awareness and legal compliance is vital for mitigating the risks connected to online journalism. Bloggers need to be provided with the necessary information pertaining to media laws, copyright laws, and ethical codes to successfully operate within the complex legal environment of digital journalism (Uche et al, 2021; 2017). Rather than imposing restrictive regulations, the legal environment needs to be designed to promote responsible journalism without undermining the openness and participatory nature of the blogosphere.

5. Strategic use of ICT tools for engagement and content credibility

Bloggers should strive to take maximum advantage of interactive tools for increasing transparency and credibility. In addition, the use of multimedia tools for content creation can improve the quality and retention of content. This would enable the relative advantage of ICT tools to be maximized by using them not only for speed but for depth and accuracy.

6. Networking and Collaboration

No man is an island, and no man is a know-it-all. Nigerian bloggers need to connect with the community of bloggers both within and outside the country. Being part of the blogging community may enable young bloggers to connect and form a network that they can use to their advantage to attain visibility. Collaboration and network formation among digital media actors is another avenue that can be explored to improve online journalism in Nigeria. Collaboration between bloggers, traditional media houses, and digital media actors may be instrumental in speeding up the transfer of knowledge and the formation of standards in the blogosphere.

7. Addressing infrastructural constraints

Lastly, addressing infrastructural constraints such as high cost of data, power supply, and access to the internet will remain crucial to improving the efficiency of the utilization of ICT. Although this issue is beyond the bloggers, it is important to note that advocacy and government support will remain crucial to promoting a suitable environment for the sustainability of online journalism in Nigeria. To avert the problem of power supply, alternative sources of power such as the sun and wind should be explored. The use of high-capacity batteries by the bloggers for their laptops and other gadgets will greatly reduce the occurrence of power outages.

Conclusion

This study has sought to explore the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the development of online journalism within the context of the blogosphere in Nigeria, with special reference to issues of credibility, sustainability, and professionalism. Through the utilization of Diffusion of Innovation Theory, this study has shown that although the utilization of ICT tools by the bloggers is widespread due to their relative advantage, compatibility, and accessibility, its utilization is still at a low level and focuses on aspects such as speed and coverage rather than accuracy and professionalism.

One of the important insights that can be derived from this analysis is that one of the main constraints to the successful utilisation of blogging as an aspect of online journalism in Nigeria is not related to technological capabilities but rather to the lack of integration of professional journalism norms with digital media. This is particularly evident in the fact that while there has been widespread adoption of ICT tools, especially those related to social media and mobile phones, there has not been a commensurate level of adoption of ethical and strategic norms.

This study, therefore, adds to the existing body of literature by changing the narrative from a purely technological approach to the study of online journalism to a more nuanced approach that appreciates the interplay between technology, professional norms, and structural conditions. This study also points to the need to move

beyond the use and access of ICT to the strategic use of ICT as a springboard for credible and sustainable journalism in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing discussion, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. There is a need to develop professional norms within the Nigerian blogosphere through training and certification programmes, as well as increased engagement with existing traditional media houses. This in turn would enhance the credibility of online journalism by incorporating ethical standards such as accountability, accuracy and verification.
2. There is the need for Nigerian bloggers to develop more advanced digital competencies, including data analytics, SEO, and multimedia content creation by instituting capacity-building programmes for the blogging community. This would improve the strategic use of ICT by reducing the perceived complexity of the tools.
3. Bloggers should also consider diversifying their income base beyond advertising revenue that is often tied to platforms by seeking opportunities in subscription-based business models, affiliate marketing, content marketing, and digital entrepreneurship opportunities. Other stakeholders in the digital space should also support the development of a framework that promotes fair monetization for content creators.
4. Educating individuals on media laws, copyright laws, and ethics is also crucial in reducing the risk of legal challenges in the journalism industry. Therefore, a balanced approach should be adopted in the regulation of media laws.
5. More collaboration should also be encouraged among bloggers, traditional media organizations, and digital platforms to enable the dissemination of knowledge among individuals.

Investing in the provision of affordable internet access, electricity, and network connectivity should also be prioritized by the relevant stakeholders to create a favourable environment for digital journalism in Nigeria.

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